

ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

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INTERNATIONAL LEGAL ASPECTS OF DIPLOMATIC IMMUNITIES AND PRIVILEGES

ANNOTATION

The article examines the scientific and legal starting points of such an institution as diplomatic immunity. Based on currently existing international legal acts, the author demonstrates that diplomatic privileges and immunities serve to ensure that diplomatic missions, which are bodies representing specific states, effectively perform their functions. Theoretical and legal aspects of diplomatic immunities and privileges in international law are also reviewed and analyzed.

Key words: immunity, diplomatic mail, receiving state, privilege, diplomatic personnel, non grata, expulsion, diplomatic immunities, Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations, criminal immunity, diplomatic representation.

ДИПЛОМАТИК ИММУНИТЕТ ВА ИМТИЁЗЛАРНИНГ ХАЛҚАРО ҲУҚУҚИЙ ЖИҲАТЛАРИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада дипломатик иммунитет институтининг илмий ва ҳуқуқий бошланғич қоидалари кўриб чиқилган. Муаллиф ҳозирда амалдаги халқаро ҳуқуқий ҳужжатларга асосланиб, дипломатик имтиёз ва иммунитетлар муайян давлатлар вакили бўлган дипломатик ваколатхоналарнинг ўз вазифаларини самарали бажаришини таъминлашга хизмат қилишини кўрсатган. Шунингдек, халқаро ҳуқуқда дипломатик иммунитет ва имтиёзларнинг назарий ва ҳуқуқий жиҳатлари кўриб чиқилган ва таҳлил қилинган.

Калит сўзлар: иммунитет, дипломатик почта, қабул қилувчи давлат, имтиёз, дипломатик ходимлар, нон грата, чиқариб юбориш, дипломатик иммунитетлар, Дипломатик муносабатлар тўғрисидаги Вена конвенцияси, жинойий дахлсизлик, дипломатик вакиллик.

МЕЖДУНАРОДНО-ПРАВОВЫЙ АСПЕКТЫ ДИПЛОМАТИЧЕСКИХ ИММУНИТЕТОВ И ПРИВИЛЕГИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье подвергаются рассмотрению научные и юридические исходные положения такого института как дипломатический иммунитет. Опираясь на действующие в данный момент международно-правовые акты, автор демонстрирует, что дипломатические привилегии и иммунитеты служат для того, чтобы диппредставительства, являющиеся органами, представляющими конкретные государства, эффективно выполняли свои функции. Также рассматриваются и анализируются теоретические и правовые аспекты дипломатических иммунитетов и привилегий в международном праве.

Ключевые слова: иммунитет, дипломатическая почта, принимающее государство, привилегия, дипломатический персонал, нон грата, высылка, дипломатические иммунитеты, Венская конвенция о дипломатических сношениях, уголовно-правовой иммунитет, дипломатическое представительство.

Diplomatic and consular immunities are individual in content, since they do not apply to the state itself, but directly to individuals. At the same time, diplomatic immunities are not given for the purpose of obtaining any advantages for individuals, but for the purpose of ensuring the effective execution of their rights and obligations by diplomatic missions on behalf of the state.

It is undeniable that the right of diplomatic immunity is mandatory for both parties. On the one hand, the person within the legal system of the recipient is given conditional privileges, and, on the other hand, the receiving state has established obligations to protect not only the diplomat himself, but also his property, so that the diplomat can effectively carry out the functions assigned to him.

The right of diplomatic and consular immunities contains both privileges for diplomatic/consular officials and obligations for the receiving country. Most attention is paid to the study conducted by K.K. Sandrovsky, privileges to immunities, as the most important element, the central institution of the entire law of foreign relations [1].

The essence of the definitions of diplomatic privileges and immunities in the literature on diplomacy and international law comes down to the following: they mean the community of some special prerogatives, rights and features, on the basis of which foreign diplomatic missions, diplomatic missions equated to foreign ones, personnel and other persons, who enjoy protection in accordance with international law in the territory of the host country.

In most cases, privileges and immunities in modern diplomatic practice are given simultaneously, in combination. But from the point of view of theory and history of the issue, there are certain differences between these concepts. Here we should agree with the opinion of M.I. Lazarev that immunity is an absolutely necessary guarantee of the normal performance of diplomatic functions, while privileges are not of such decisive importance and only facilitate the work of the diplomat and the mission as a whole, contributing to its successful completion [2].

In connection with the differences between privileges and immunities noted above, the position of K.K. Sandrovsky comes down to the fact that the norms of international law that provide for them also differ in the degree of their obligatory nature [3].

Most of these rules are of a dispositive nature, which allows either expanding or reducing the scope of benefits, privileges and immunities provided for by general international law, provided, however, that such a modification or derogation will not be incompatible with the mandatory principles and norms that govern relations between countries.

The importance of diplomatic activity in international relations cannot be overestimated. Even in the modern period of historical development, the rapid development of direct and instant communications, nothing can compete with the individual and trusted connections between diplomatic agents and representatives of the host country. As a result, the law of diplomatic immunities acts as one of the most important institutions of international law.

As stated in the International Court of Justice in the 1980 Tehran American embassy siege case (US v. Iran), these rules are “fundamental in nature”, constituting a jus cogens (peremptory norm), and their steadfastness is “vital to the reliability of and the prosperity of today's complex international community.”

International law establishing the legal principles of consular and diplomatic immunities is enshrined in two fundamental conventions - the Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations 1961 (currently 190 parties) [4] and the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations 1963 (currently 179 parties) [5].

This article will pay close attention to the Convention on Diplomatic Relations and references to “the Convention” should be considered references to that treaty. Although consular officers perform vital administrative functions concerning citizens in the country to which they are accredited, the most important political and representative work falls on diplomatic agents. In the vast majority of situations, the immunities and privileges of consular workers are not as extensive as those of diplomatic workers.

The Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations came into force on April 24, 1964 and, as we noted above, as of April 1, 2014, there were 190 contracting parties. This Convention is the result of the work of the UN Conference on Diplomatic Relations and Immunities in 1961.

The initial provisions of this Convention were a number of draft articles that were prepared by the International Law Commission (ILC). Based on the usual principle of international treaties, only states that have ratified the Convention are bound by specific obligations.

However, it cannot be firmly said that the Convention was mainly the result of the codification of existing international legal norms, or is their progressive development. As the International Court of Justice recorded in the case of the United States v. Iran, at this time the bulk of the Convention reproduces customary international law and it is absolutely clear that almost all controversial issues regarding diplomatic law can be resolved in accordance with the provisions and obligations of this treaty. It was originally believed that the basis of diplomatic privileges rested on the status and position of the head of state. For this reason, it followed that diplomats are a kind of representatives or alter ego of the sovereign and are obliged to have all the immunities that the sovereign would have.

Similarly, the rules relating to the protection and inviolability of a diplomatic mission - embassy, were formed on the basis that the mission acts as part of the independent territory of the sending state. However, over time it became clear that these two provisions distort the meaning of diplomatic and consular immunities.

The purpose of diplomatic immunities is expressed in ensuring the effective performance of the functions of diplomatic representatives of their state without fear of persecution from the authorities of the receiving state.

The basis of diplomatic immunities is functionality, and therefore the diplomat is granted established privileges and immunities, and the receiving state is assigned specific obligations. This judgment is correct even if certain immunities also apply to situations where a diplomat does not exercise his official powers, but he uses the immunity in personal or individual affairs.

Again, this is done to avoid doubt that the diplomat is not under any form of pressure from the receiving state. As the introductory part of the Vienna Convention explains, “such privileges and immunities are not granted for the benefit of individuals, but to ensure the effective exercise of the functions of diplomatic missions representing States” [6] as bodies, the provisions of the Vienna Convention apply to several categories of persons that are specified in art. . 1, and who enjoy some or all of the immunities.

These individuals include the head of a diplomatic mission (e.g., ambassador or charge d'affaires), members of the diplomatic staff (diplomats), members of the administrative and technical staff (secretaries, etc.), members of the service staff (e.g., kitchen staff, housekeeping staff)) and private domestic workers (for example, personal valet). In most cases, the broadest immunities are given to the head of mission and his diplomatic staff, and to the least extent to other categories of employees.

The same degree of diplomatic immunities that are granted to the head of mission, diplomats or administrative and technical staff also covers members of their families. However, if there is no special agreement, then for persons who are citizens of the host country, immunities can be granted only to the extent necessary for them to carry out their official duties, and for service personnel there are no such immunities at all.

The most significant personal immunities are contained in Art. 29 and 31 of the Convention. The person of a diplomatic agent (including the head of mission) enjoys immunity. He cannot be arrested or detained in any form. A diplomatic agent located in the receiving State must be accorded appropriate respect, and all possible measures must be taken to prevent any attacks on the freedom, dignity or person of this diplomatic agent (Article 29 of the Convention).

In accordance with Art. 31 of the Convention, the diplomatic agent has absolute immunity from criminal prosecution of the host country, and he also has immunity from administrative and civil jurisdiction, with the exception of claims that relate to transactions with personal real estate; relate to inheritance disputes; relate to any professional or commercial activity carried out outside the boundaries of his official authority.

For example, a diplomat has immunity from parking tickets, shoplifting, sexual assault and other criminal offenses, as well as from most civil suits. However, diplomatic agents do not have immunity from civil claims that relate to personal business advice or non-staff “commercial activities.” For the most part, members of a diplomat's family enjoy the same immunities, even if they are not citizens of the host country [7].

Administrative and technical workers and members of their families have similar immunities. But there is an exception - immunity from civil and administrative jurisdiction of these persons extends only to their official acts that they perform in the performance of their functions.

Administrative and technical workers and members of their families lose immunity if they are citizens of the host country or permanently reside on its territory (Article 37). The immunities of other categories of employees have been greatly reduced.

Other immunities, again in varying amounts for different categories, include exemption from taxes, customs duties, as well as from all labor and government obligations (for example, from conscription or participation in a jury trial).

In accordance with Art. 22 of the Convention, in the absence of the consent of the head of the diplomatic mission, any authorities of the host state do not have the right to enter the premises of the embassy (diplomatic mission), since the latter is inviolable.

The term “premises of mission” means any buildings, including the residence of the head of the mission, and the land plot under them, regardless of the ownership of them (Article 1). In addition, the property and vehicles of the mission are immune from search and seizure (Article 22), and any archival documents of the diplomatic mission are inviolable even when they are located outside the premises of the diplomatic mission (Article 24).

The host country has a duty to protect mission premises (Article 22) and is liable under international law if it fails to provide adequate protection. Such immunities and the duty to protect embassy buildings remain in force even if there is a rupture of diplomatic relations or an armed conflict (Article 45).

But this applies only as long as the premises of the diplomatic mission are used for diplomatic purposes. The personal residence of a member of the diplomatic staff has the same inviolability as the embassy itself, and his documents and correspondence are also inviolable, except in cases that relate to matters subject to civil jurisdiction (Article 30).

Such immunities also apply to members of administrative and technical personnel who are not citizens of the host state or permanently residing on its territory. According to Art. 26, the receiving country is obliged to protect and defend the right of free movement within its territory.

But there is an exception to this rule, which states that the right of free movement does not apply in those zones into which entry is prohibited or regulated for reasons of national security. Along with this in Art. 27 of the Convention stipulates that the host country must undoubtedly provide and protect free communication between diplomatic missions in the implementation of all its public missions.

The article demonstratively provides permission to use encryption of information transmitted to one's government or when communicating with other embassies of the accrediting state, however, the radio transmitter can only be used with the permission of the receiving state. All correspondence that relates to the mission and its functions is inviolable and, importantly, diplomatic mail can neither be opened nor detained.

And this is despite the size of the "mail", which can range from an aircraft filled with pallet boxes to a small package of papers - if the "mail" has noticeable external signs, then it cannot comply with the standard import procedure.

In recent years, the problem of the inviolability of diplomatic mail has become a source of serious concern for many states. There have been cases where diplomatic pouches have been used to smuggle drugs, weapons, art treasures or even people into or out of the receiving state.

Although Art. 27(4) stipulates that diplomatic mail must contain only "documents and articles intended for official use", however, the provision that the receiving State cannot open the mail for inspection remains absolute.

It is not surprising that, due to the likelihood of abuses, slogans for changing the provisions on the inviolability of diplomatic mail began to be heard more and more often, and the International Law Commission undertook a scrupulous study of the law of diplomatic correspondence. At this time, as part of its work, the Draft Articles on Diplomatic Couriers and Diplomatic Mail were prepared, which is intended to lay down a comprehensive system and become the basis of a multilateral treaty.

The most important innovations are contained in Art. 28 – Protection of diplomatic mail. The International Law Commission held a large number of meetings on the issue of this innovation. At these meetings, some participants preferred unconditional immunity, while others preferred the "open or return" rule.

The draft article generally takes the side of the first of them: "diplomatic mail is inviolable regardless of its location; it is not subject to opening or detention and is exempt from any inspection directly or by electronic or other technical means." Let us note that in Art. 28 (2) of the Draft Articles for consular mail, the "opening or returning" rule is retained [8].

After extensive discussion, the ILC was inclined to believe in the absolute inviolability of the diplomatic bag, and the draft articles are aimed at increasing the security of diplomatic relations.

So, the vast majority of discussions that relate to diplomatic law are regulated by the rules enshrined in the Vienna Convention. There is no doubt that a significant part of the provisions of the Vienna Convention represents the codification of customary international law.

It is not surprising that the increased abuse of diplomatic privileges by some diplomats in recent years has led to growing demands that diplomats be granted less absolute immunities.

However, with the adoption of the Draft Articles on the Diplomatic Post, such demands have not yet found support in the ILC. Of course, it is difficult to accept the fact that narrowing the scope of these immunities in favor of the host state will definitely benefit everyone.

The introduction of a limit on diplomatic immunities would be permissible if we clearly saw that states are not making any efforts to apply such metamorphoses exclusively for their own purposes.

Reducing immunities in relation to diplomats or diplomatic property will only embolden those states that are already flouting international law. Such liberties in the uncompromising nature of the Vienna Convention will only provoke new unwanted incidents.

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